

Statistical Mechanics: Time Averages Mapped Into a Fictitious Equilibrium Spatial Representation?

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Statistical mechanics is presented in a variety of ways including factorial counting schemes, partition functions and reaction balance. It may be difficult to discern the ideas and links between these. In this note, we try to examine the idea of independent particles which change energy states in time. Thus, we argue that $f(e/T)$ represents a time average. This time average $f(e/T)$ yields reaction balance equations which are identical to specific spatial reactions of a few particles and so, it seems, a time average has been mapped into a spatial representation. One imagines a fictitious equilibrium system which exists at a specific point in time and contains $f(e_i/T)$ particles with energy e_i , even if such a scenario does not ever physically exist at any point in time, it is useful for reaction balance equations.

The Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) Distribution

The MB distribution seems to consist of N independent particles which may interact through elastic two body collisions. If one follows a particle in time, it changes from e_1 to e_2 to e_3 etc. $f(e_i)$ yields the probability (in time) that a particle is found in state e_i , but $N f(e_i)$ (N =number of particles) also represent the number of particles in a fictitious equilibrium state that exists at one instant in time. To see why such a state is possibly fictitious, consider the following. Imagine one has a series of representations of N particles, each with a total energy E and each has a weight of 1. This is usually taken as a foundational idea of statistical mechanics. It is also linked to the idea of maximum uncertainty, because no one state is more likely than another. Each state is physical and may be considered as existing at an instant in time. For example, one state may have a particle with energy E and $N-1$ particles with energy 0, or two particles with $E/2$ and $N-2$ with energy 0 etc. One may calculate $f(e_i)$ by taking an average over all of these states. Thus, $f(e_i)$ represents the average time a particle spends in e_i over time. $N f(e_i)$ is associated with a fictitious state at an instant in time with $N f(e_i)$ particles having energy e_i . To see it is fictitious, one may note there is a probability for a particle to have energy E , but that means all of the other particles have energy 0, so $f(e_i)$ is a time average.

The fictitious macrostate existing at an instant preserves the probabilities of a two body elastic collision, thus one may apply reaction balance i.e.:

$$f(e_1)f(e_2) = f(e_3)f(e_4) \text{ and } e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4 \quad ((1))$$

Here $f(e_i)$'s are averages over time, but they have been mapped into a fictitious spatial representation which exists at an instant.

One may further see that this reaction balance is not based on any overall macro-energy E . Rather, from ((1)) one finds that $f(e_i) = \exp(-e_i/u/T)$ and calculates an average E in time and

normalizes $f(e_i)$ to 1 (or N). This seems to follow because one treats particles as being independent and uses the constraint:

$$\sum_i e_i f(e_i) = E \quad ((2))$$

Here, $f(e_i)$ is a time average, so E itself may be considered to be an average value as well.

Consider the following approach to calculating $f(e_i)$ using factorials. Imagine $f(e_i)$ is the probability for a single particle to be in a state e_i in time. Imagine M slices of time. Then, a particle is in state e_i for $M f(e_i)$ of these slices. To maximize uncertainty of energy state in time, one may maximize:

$$\ln\{ M! / (m_1! M_2! M_3! \dots) \} \text{ subject to the constraints } \sum m_i = M \text{ and } \sum e_i m_i = E \quad ((3))$$

Where $m_i = N f(e_i)$. Performing such a maximization leads to $m_i = N \exp(-(e_i - u)/T)$.

Here we use the idea that the average energy of a particle in time is E/N .

Although ((3)) applies to a time average, it seems to be clearer to map it into a fictitious spatial representation, the "equilibrium" picture, at an instant in time. Then, at this instant there are $N f(e_i)$ particles in e_i and they interact as $f(e_i)f(e_j) = f(e_k)f(e_l)$ where $e_i + e_j = e_k + e_l$ to provide a balance.

Fermi-Dirac (FD) Distribution

The FD case of fermions allows one to immediately see the fictitious nature of the equilibrium spatial representation as well as the presence of the grand canonical partition function. The fermion occupation of a state is either 0 or 1 (ignoring spin), but one may imagine a time average $f(e_i)$ which is equivalent to the probability in time for the fermion to be in state e_i . Thus, if there are M slices of time, the fermion is present $M f(e_i)$ of the time and absent $M(1 - f(e_i))$ of the time. In order to maximize the uncertainty of finding the fermion in state e_i in any slice of time, one may maximize

$$\ln\{ \text{Product over } i \ M! / [f(e_i)! [(1 - f(e_i))!]] \} \text{ subject to } \sum_i f(e_i) = \text{constant} \text{ and } \sum_i e_i f(e_i) = \text{constant } E. \quad ((4))$$

Thus, one considers M slices in time, each called M_i . For each fermion, one has a set of vectors $(0, 1, 0, 0, 1, \dots)$ where 1 means the fermion is present at time i and 0 that it is not. One may see that if one combines various vectors for different fermions, each combination may contain a different total energy and total particle number at each instant in time. It is only in the time average that one has $\langle N \rangle$ particles and $\langle E \rangle$ energy. Thus, this time average for fermions is equivalent to a grand canonical partition function. One would still have to prove that the weights are $\exp(-(E - uN)/T)$, but the solution of ((4)) is equivalent to such a result with $N = \sum_i n_i$ and $n_i = 0$ or 1 and $E = \sum_i n_i e_i$.

Alternatively, one may imagine a fictitious equilibrium spatial distribution existing at a point in time with $f(e_i)$ being the probability for a fermion to be in energy state e_i . Then, applying reaction balance to $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$, one has:

$$f(e_1)[1-f(e_3)] f(e_2)[1-f(e_4)] = f(e_1)[1-f(e_3)]f(e_4)[1-f(e_2)] \quad ((5))$$

Bose-Einstein (BE) Distribution

The BE distribution is a little trickier. One again has an average over time yielding $f((e_i-u)/T)$, which maps into a fictitious equilibrium distribution in space existing at a point in time. The scattering equation using average $f(e_i)$ values should still match that for a regular reaction of several particles (1) (not related to statistical mechanics). Thus, for $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$:

$$f(e_1) [1+f(e_3)] f(e_2) [1+f(e_4)] = f(e_2)[1+f(e_3)]f(e_4)[1+f(e_2)] \quad ((6))$$

From a regular scattering of bosons scenario, (without statistical mechanics), the probability of having n_i bosons in state e_i is enhanced by $n_i!$. Thus, the fictitious equilibrium state associated with the RHS of ((6)) seems to be:

$$\text{Product over } i \quad [f(e_i)+1]! / f(e_i)! \quad ((7))$$

One may maximize the \ln of ((7)) subject to the usual constraints $\sum \text{over } i \quad f(e_i) = \langle N \rangle$ and $\sum \text{over } i \quad e_i f(e_i) = \langle E \rangle$. Thus, because one may map the time average into a fictitious spatial system and apply reaction balance, one may also find a corresponding factorial representation.

If one had a new particle with the following reaction rule:

$$f(e_1) [1+f(e_3)]^q f(e_2) [1+f(e_4)]^q = f(e_2)[1+f(e_3)]^q f(e_4)[1+f(e_2)]^q \quad ((8))$$

Where q is an integer, one would create a factorial scheme:

$$\text{Product over } i \quad [f(e_i)+1]!^q / f(e_i)! \quad ((9))$$

Fluctuations

The idea that $f(e_i)$ is a time average may have an effect on the idea of fluctuations. $f(e_i)$ is the number of particles or probability of the fictitious equilibrium scenario, but it is equivalent to the average of many systems each with total E_i and N_i . Thus, the overall fictitious equilibrium state already averages over what one would call fluctuations. One may, however, consider fluctuations in time for which $f(e_i)$ is not the time average.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it seems that statistical mechanics is usually represented in terms of configurations or arrangements in space. We argue that it is based on an average in time such that these averages may be mapped into a fictitious spatial equilibrium situation which allows for reaction balance using $f(e_i)$ time average values as if they were actual probabilities or numbers of particles in a reaction which was not necessarily even associated with statistical mechanics.

References

1. Feynman, R. Lecture Notes https://www.feynmanlectures.caltech.edu/III_04.html